

Habits and attitudes of respondents towards probiotics

Azira Hrnjica^{1*}, Huska Jukić¹, Elma Beriša¹, Sadat Kurtalić², Samir Porić¹

¹Faculty of Health Studies, Bihać, Bosnia and Herzegovina

²Department of Internal Medicine, Cantonal Hospital "Dr. Irfan Ljubijankić", Bihać, Bosnia and Herzegovina

*E-mail: azira.hrnjica@unbi.ba

Abstract. Probiotics are live microorganisms that, when ingested in sufficient quantities, contribute to maintaining the balance of the gut microbiota, strengthening the immune system, preventing and treating certain diseases, and improving mental health. The aim of the research was to examine the level of awareness, habits and attitudes of consumers towards probiotics, with special emphasis on the forms of probiotics and the reasons for their use. The research was conducted with an online questionnaire on a sample of 122 respondents of different ages and genders. The results showed that awareness of probiotics is very high (98%), and 80% of respondents actively use them. The majority of respondents use probiotics only when necessary, while a smaller number of respondents practice daily use. These results indicate a positive attitude of the general population towards the importance of probiotics in preserving health. This indicates the justification and the need for further education in order to reduce information gaps and increase the use of probiotics in everyday life.

1. Introduction

The beneficial effects of probiotic food on human health have been increasingly recognized by health professionals over time. Scientific studies suggest that probiotics play an important role in immune, digestive, and respiratory functions. Over the past 20 years, research in the field of probiotics has made significant progress, and there has been considerable advancement in the selection and characterization of specific probiotic cultures and substantiating health claims related to their consumption. Bacteria are normal inhabitants of humans, including the gastrointestinal tract, where more than 400 bacterial species are found. Concentration of microorganisms in the large intestine is approximately 10^{12} bacteria/g. Bacterial colonization of the gut begins at birth and continues throughout life, with specific age-related flora changes. Bacteria, which form the resident intestinal microflora, do not have any acute side effects and some of them are necessary to maintain human well-being [1]. Due to all these scientific knowledge about their well-being, it is recommended to consume probiotic food or take probiotics in the form of nutritional supplements. In today's fast-paced lifestyle, dietary supplements offer a simple way to consume probiotics.

The aim of the research was to determine the reasons for the use of probiotics, a source of information about their health benefits, and the frequency and form of their use. The goal was also to assess the user satisfaction with the effect of probiotics and to point out the potential benefits of their use. The obtained data can serve as a basis for further research and education of consumers about the importance of probiotics in everyday nutrition.

2. Theory

2.1 Development of probiotics, their types and functions

The works of Metchnikoff and Tissier were the first to make scientific proposals regarding the probiotic use of bacteria. The word "probiotic" was coined in 1960 to describe substances produced by microorganisms that promote the growth of other microorganisms. The term probiotic is a relatively new word used to describe bacteria that have beneficial effects on humans and animals.

The first observations of the positive role of selected bacteria are attributed to Eli Metchnikoff, a Russian Nobel Prize winner who claimed that it is possible to replace harmful flora with beneficial microbes in the gastrointestinal tract and that intestinal flora also depends on food [1]. Henry Tissier isolated *Bifidobacterium* from the intestines of infants and found that the presence of these bacteria reduced the incidence of diarrhea. This discovery led to the idea of the therapeutic use of bifidobacteria for the treatment of gastrointestinal disorders. Minoru Shirota isolated *Lactobacillus casei* in Japan in 1930. Until 1935, Minoru Shirota developed the milk drink "Yakult," claiming that regular consumption improves the digestive system and contributes to longevity. The product has been available on the market since 1935 and is one of the first commercial probiotic products [2]. From the mid-20th century, the focus of research shifted to the medical uses of probiotics. World Health Organization and Food and Agriculture Organization in 2001 developed a definition of probiotics as "living microorganisms which, when used in appropriate amounts, bring a health effect to the host" [3].

There are 86 different types of probiotics, each with different functions. Among the most common types of probiotics are *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Bifidobacterium longum* and *Saccharomyces boulardii*. *Lactobacillus acidophilus* is a bacterium found naturally in the digestive system, urinary tract and other parts of the body. It produces lactic acid from lactose through the enzyme lactase and thus helps create an acidic environment, which prevents the growth of pathogenic bacteria. It occurs naturally in fermented dairy products and naturally fermented foods [4,5]. *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* is part of the normal microbiota in approximately 8% of humans. This bacterium strengthens the immune system and is used in therapy for treating viral gastroenteritis. It also participates in the production of short-chain fatty acids, restores the intestinal mucosa, reduces the risk of colon cancer and accelerates recovery from allergies. *Bifidobacterium longum* is one of the first bacteria to colonize the sterile digestive system of newborns, and thus plays an important role in the development of their immune system. This bacterium prevents the entry and spread of pathogenic microorganisms, breaks down bile salts, participates in the synthesis of vitamins from group B, and shows anticancer properties. Additionally, it stimulates the immune system through immunoglobulin A, producing acetic and lactic acid that reduce the pH value in the intestines [6]. *Saccharomyces boulardii* is one of the rare probiotic yeasts known for its resistance to gastric acid and bile salts, which enables it to survive in the gastrointestinal tract. It helps maintain the health of the intestinal microflora, especially after the use of antibiotics or chemotherapy. It is used in the prevention and treatment of diarrhea and to prevent the growth of pathogenic microorganisms [7]. Few studies have been published on the beneficial immunomodulatory effects of probiotics. Studies are mainly focused on the metabolic and nutritional properties of probiotics, therefore the mechanisms of interaction between host immune cells and probiotics are only partially described.

One of the mechanisms of immunomodulatory activity is described in a paper by Mazziotta et al. (2023) as the interactive potential of probiotic bacteria with immune cells as well as

intestinal epithelial cells. It has been stated that probiotics can improve the immune system of the gut by stimulating B cells to produce IgA. So, taking different probiotics orally, e.g. *Lactobacillus casei* or *Streptococcus thermophilus* increases the number of intestinal cells that produce IgA in a dose-dependent manner. *Lactobacillus casei* and *rhamnosus GG* have been shown to be effective in stimulating an immune response against rotavirus in children with acute diarrhoea. This probiotic effectiveness in immunomodulating responses against rotavirus has been documented, and currently, a large number of probiotics are recommended for treating diarrhea and other gastrointestinal diseases. In the treatment of these diseases, lactobacilli are currently considered the most effective bacteria [8]. Another important function of probiotics is metabolic function. The microbiota participates in the digestion of complex food molecules, the production of short-chain fatty acids, and the synthesis of vitamins such as vitamin K and B complex [9].

3. Materials and methods

The paper uses scientific methods of description, deductive and inductive methods. The sample method, surveys, statistical method and empirical-non-experimental method were also used. The research was conducted using a survey questionnaire on the perception, attitudes and habits of the respondents in relation to probiotics. The survey questionnaire was created using the online platform "Google Forms". The questionnaire was anonymous and contained a total of 13 open-ended and multiple-choice questions. The questions included demographic data (age, gender), knowledge of probiotics, reasons for their use or avoidance, frequency of use, satisfaction with the effect of probiotics, and possible obstacles in their use. The target population included adults of various age groups, and a total of 122 participants voluntarily participated in the study. Data collection lasted a week, during which all responses were recorded anonymously. „Microsoft Excel“ was used for additional processing and more detailed data analysis.

4. Results

A total of 122 respondents participated in the research, of which 46% were 15-24 years old, 39% were 24-39 years old, and 15% were 50 years old or older. According to the gender distribution of the respondents, 61% were women and 39% were men. The questionnaire was filled out by respondents from all over Bosnia and Herzegovina. Figure 1 shows the sources of information on probiotics in subjects.

Figure 1. How subjects get information about probiotics

The reasons for which the subjects use probiotics are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Reasons for using probiotics in the subjects

The form of probiotics most commonly consumed by the subjects is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The most commonly consumed forms of probiotics in subjects

The frequency of probiotic consumption in subjects is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Frequency of probiotic consumption in subjects

81% of respondents agreed that probiotics have a beneficial effect on human health.

5. Discussion

Research results indicate a high level of awareness and use of probiotics among the subjects, confirming that probiotics have become a significant part of dietary and health habits. The age group of respondents shows that the majority of respondents are younger people (15 to 24 years old), which may be a consequence of their greater availability to participate in research or greater interest in the topic. The gender structure shows a higher representation of women in the sample, which may be the result of their greater interest in participating in the study or their greater focus on health and dietary habits. Internet, as the second most common source of

information, is easily accessible and often used, but one must be cautious as it can contain unreliable information and may be subject to marketing bias. Due to the lack of regulation in the probiotic industry, marketing of probiotic products is often directed directly at consumers without any indication of their actual clinical effectiveness. This trend highlights the need to provide adequate indications for the use of probiotics by scientists or clinicians. Different international scientific societies/agencies, such as the *American Gastroenterological Association* (AGA), the *European Society for Paediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition* (ESPGHAN), and others, they assessed the clinical reliability of probiotics and provided official recommendations for their use in treating gastrointestinal disorders in humans, such as diarrhea, colitis, acute gastroenteritis, irritable bowel syndrome and necrotizing enterocolitis [8]. However, the Internet plays an important role, especially among younger generations, who rely more on digital sources of information. Therefore, it is important to pay attention to the relevance of the information sources available on the Internet and to consider only those that come from medical and scientific professionals. Education enables the acquisition of basic and reliable information about probiotics, their properties and ways of use.

The most common reason for using probiotics among the subjects was to improve digestion, which is in accordance with the literature that confirms the importance of probiotics in preserving the balance of intestinal microflora. The next most common reason for consuming probiotics among the respondents was strengthening the immune system, which further emphasizes the importance of using probiotics for this purpose.

Most respondents use probiotics in the form of dietary supplements, which can be explained by their practicality, ease of use and availability on the market. Dietary supplements often come in the form of capsules, tablets or powders, which enables precise dosing, which makes them suitable for the specific needs of users. Fermented dairy products, such as yogurt and kefir, are used by a significant number of subjects, which indicates the popularity of these foods as a natural source of probiotics. These products are often available in stores and are considered a tasty and healthy option for maintaining a balanced gut microbiota. Naturally fermented products, such as sauerkraut and other traditional fermented foods, are used significantly less. This difference can be explained by the lower availability of these products in today's daily diet, as well as less awareness of their health effects.

The results show that most subjects consume probiotics only as needed. Most often, this can be associated with the use of probiotics during antibiotic therapy. Antibiotics destroy not only pathogenic bacteria, but also beneficial bacteria that are important for maintaining the balance of intestinal microbiota. The use of the targeted sequencing method has shown that antibiotics cause a decrease in the biomass of intestinal bacteria, their taxonomic diversity and functionality. This often leads to dysbiosis, a condition that can cause symptoms such as diarrhea, bloating, or a general decrease in the body's resistance to infections. Probiotics help restore a healthy gut microbiological composition, reducing the risk of complications and speeding recovery. For these reasons, probiotics are considered useful during and after antibiotic treatment [10].

Miles (2020) conducted a study that showed the effectiveness of the use of supplementation with multi-strain probiotics in athletes in reducing the frequency and severity of gastrointestinal symptoms during training or competition, quantitatively expressed by one third. The interesting thing about this study is that the probability of effectiveness increased with the duration of supplementation. It appears that probiotics taken for at least 11 weeks have shown the greatest effectiveness in reducing the frequency and severity of gastrointestinal symptoms, as well as

improving or maintaining the function of the intestinal barrier during training and competition [11].

6. Conclusion

Probiotics have a positive effect on human health; they have protective, immunomodulatory and metabolic functions. To have a positive effect on human health, probiotics must be ingested in the appropriate quantity. It is precisely the ease of taking and dosing that has made probiotics in the form of dietary supplements the most commonly taken form of probiotics. In addition to dietary supplements, good sources of probiotics are fermented dairy products and fermented products. From this study, it can be concluded that Bosnian citizens have a positive attitude towards probiotics and believe in their well-being for health. The most common use of probiotics is mostly only if necessary. However, it has been proven that the effectiveness of probiotics in reducing gastrointestinal symptoms increases with longer supplementation. The Internet is a frequent source of information about probiotics, and therefore it should be considered useful, but also used with caution, that is, only relevant articles written by medical or health professionals should be taken into account.

7. References

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